

Sampling: comparison of means**Options**

Type I error (Alpha,Significance):	0.01
Type II error (Beta, 1-Power):	0.01

Data

Difference of means	423
Standard deviation in group 1	304
Standard deviation in group 2	324

Result

Number of cases required in Group 1:	28
Number of cases required in Group 2:	28
Total sample size (both groups together):	56

Table

		Type I Error - Alpha			
		0.20	0.10	0.05	0.01
Type II Error - Beta	0.20	6 + 6	8 + 8	10 + 10	14 + 14
	0.10	8 + 8	10 + 10	13 + 13	18 + 18
	0.05	10 + 10	13 + 13	15 + 15	21 + 21
	0.01	15 + 15	18 + 18	21 + 21	28 + 28